

The Influence of Teacher Discipline Dimensions on the Quality of the Teaching and Learning Process at MIS Al-Hilal Wanakarta School, Lolong Guba District, Buru Regency

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine how the quality of teaching and learning process at Mis Al-Hilal Wanakarta school is impacted by the aspects of teacher discipline. This study employs quantitative approach and uses saturated sample which involves twelve teachers. The data is gathered by observation, questionnaires with five possible answers on a Likert scale score choice form that are distributed to twelve teachers, and documentation as a supplementary method. The data is analyzed using a straightforward linear regression test that includes Spearman rank correlation and the determination coefficient test, t test, or partial test, and F test, or simultaneous test. According to the study's findings, (H_0) is rejected and (H_a) is accepted, indicating a strong and positive relationship between the aspects of teacher discipline and the quality of teaching and learning process. This is supported by the Spearman rank correlation coefficient value of 0.6137. Based on the R Square value of 0.517 obtained from the simple linear regression test, there is a 51.7% impact of the teacher discipline aspects on the quality of teaching and learning process. The results of the t test shows that the variable aspects of teacher discipline have a significant impact on the quality of the teaching and learning process (t value (3.269) > t table (1.812) with a significance of 0.008 < 0.05), and the results of the F test shows that the F value is 10.683 with a significance of 0.008 < 0.05.

Abstrak

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengungkapkan pengaruh dimensi disiplin guru terhadap kualitas proses belajar mengajar pada sekolah Mis Al-Hilal Wanakarta. Penelitian menggunakan metode kuantitatif dengan sampel jenuh yang melibatkan 12 orang guru. Pengumpulan data dilakukan melalui observasi, kuesioner yang disebarikan kepada 12 orang guru dengan menggunakan bentuk pilihan skor skala likert yakni 5 alternatif jawaban, dan dokumentasi sebagai teknik pelengkap dalam pengumpulan data. Analisis data menggunakan uji regresi linear sederhana yang terdiri dari (uji koefisien determinasi, uji t atau uji parsial, & uji F atau uji simultan) dan korelasi Spearman rank. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa H_0 ditolak dan H_a diterima, artinya dimensi disiplin guru berpengaruh positif dan signifikan terhadap kualitas proses belajar mengajar, dibuktikan dengan nilai koefisien korelasi Spearman rank sebesar 0,6137 yang menunjukkan hubungan yang kuat. Hasil uji regresi linear sederhana menghasilkan nilai R Square sebesar 0,517, yang berarti dimensi disiplin guru mempengaruhi kualitas proses belajar mengajar sebesar 51,7%. Uji t menghasilkan nilai t hitung (3,269) > t tabel (1,812) dengan signifikansi 0,008 < 0,05, dan uji F menghasilkan nilai F hitung sebesar 10,683 dengan signifikansi 0,008 < 0,05, yang keduanya mengonfirmasi pengaruh signifikan variabel dimensi disiplin guru terhadap kualitas proses belajar mengajar.

Kata Kunci : Dimensi Disiplin Guru, Kualitas Proses Belajar Mengajar

INTRODUCTION

Education is a fundamental foundation for human resource development and the progress of a nation. Therefore, the education system continues to be updated and improved so that its implementation can produce the expected generation. According to Law No. 20 of 2003 on the National Education System, education is defined as a conscious and planned effort to create a learning environment and learning process in which students actively develop their potential. The goal is for them to possess spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and the skills needed by themselves, society, the nation, and the state.

According to Ki Hajar Dewantara as cited by Ab Marisyah (2019), education is a fundamental effort to instill spiritual and cultural values that exist in society, which has its own cultural heritage passed down from generation to generation. Education is not only about maintaining those values but also about advancing and developing culture. Ki Hajar Dewantara elaborates that the goals of education are divided into three parts: to shape students' noble character; to enhance their intellectual capabilities, and to ensure their physical health.

To achieve these educational goals, education must be guided by a coherent set of principles, including Ing Ngarsa Sung Tuladha (teachers as role models), Ing Madya Mangun Karsa (teachers as motivators and idea developers), and Tut Wuri Handayani (teachers providing guidance and encouragement). Education also plays a vital role in shaping students' individual behavior so that they are better prepared to interact with their environment. The implication of this process significantly impacts a nation's progress as it produces educated individuals who understand themselves, become better people, increase their creativity, empathy, and develop leadership skills.

Primary education institutions hold a crucial role in improving the quality of human resources. This is because elementary schools serve as the foundation for developing quality education, where students are equipped with basic skills necessary to continue to the next level of education. In the context of the system, schools comprise various interconnected elements that contribute to achieving educational goals, such as curriculum, learning materials, students, teachers, school principals, infrastructure, and other supporting personnel. While students are the main focus, teachers are responsible for shaping their character.

Teachers with good performance will certainly succeed in fulfilling their duties as educators. However, in reality, the performance of teachers is still generally suboptimal and requires improvement. One reason is the tendency of teachers to perform their duties merely as routines, without sufficient creativity. Innovation is often viewed as foreign, and creativity is not considered part of performance. This condition indicates a serious need to improve the quality and performance of educators in Indonesia.

MIS Al-Hilaal Wanakarta is an educational institution equivalent to an elementary school, which is the focus of this study. Observations of the learning process at MIS Al-Hilaal Wanakarta indicate that its implementation is still not optimal, resulting in many students being unable to fully develop their potential. In the context of learning, the availability and use of learning resources play a crucial role. Learning resources refer to all elements in the learning environment that contribute to achieving optimal learning outcomes. However, many educators are still unable to utilize these resources effectively. For example, many teachers still rely heavily on the lecture method, which is generally one-directional. As a result, the learning process becomes monotonous and less engaging, ultimately leading to student boredom.

This phenomenon further highlights the ineffective use of learning resources in the learning process. This condition requires serious attention, considering the importance of variety and innovation in teaching methods to improve the quality of education and optimize students' potential. Solutions may include training, workshops, or other professional development programs focusing on the creative and interactive use of learning resources.

In realizing the goals of education, the role of the teacher is extremely crucial. Teachers are not only responsible for transferring knowledge but also for shaping character and developing students' potential. They are at the forefront of the education process and directly influence the quality of learning. However, the reality on the ground shows that the quality of education in Indonesia still does not meet

the desired standards. This is reflected in unsatisfactory teacher competency evaluation results and low national exam achievements in several provinces.

One important factor affecting teacher performance and the quality of the teaching-learning process is discipline. According to Muchdarsyah Sinungun as cited by Fikriyah (2022), discipline is a mental attitude reflected in the behavior of individuals, groups, or communities as obedience to regulations or norms established by the government or societal ethics. Discipline, as stated by Arifudin (2020), is a rule or behavior adopted by the community and is especially important in school and community environments. As social beings, humans live among others and must discipline themselves, both in school and outside, including in their workplaces.

Although teacher discipline is very important, field observations show that there are still discipline-related problems among teachers, particularly at MIS Al-Hilaal Wanakarta. These include lateness in arriving at school, late entry to class, unexplained absences, leaving class before the session ends, and using teaching time for personal matters. Such lack of discipline not only disrupts the learning process but also sets a bad example for students. Tardiness and lack of discipline reduce learning time and hinder students' academic development. Furthermore, many teachers have yet to fully utilize varied learning media, even though such media play a key role in achieving optimal learning outcomes.

This study is expected to make a significant contribution to improving the quality of education, particularly by enhancing teacher discipline and optimizing the teaching-learning process. The research findings could serve as a basis for policy decisions and strategies to improve teacher discipline, which in turn will positively impact the quality of learning. Additionally, this research could provide new insights into the importance of discipline in the teaching profession and serve as a reflection for educators to continuously improve their professionalism.

Considering the importance of teacher discipline in improving the quality of the teaching-learning process, in-depth research is needed to examine the relationship between teacher discipline and the quality of teaching and learning. Based on the issues described above, the writer is encouraged to conduct a study titled: "The Influence of Teacher Discipline Dimensions on the Quality of the Teaching-Learning Process at MIS Al-Hilaal Wanakarta, Lolong Guba District, Buru Regency."

METHOD

This research uses a quantitative approach, as stated by Sugiyono (2007:31), who explained that quantitative research begins with abstract concepts, then focuses on theoretical frameworks to form hypotheses that are tested empirically. The study was conducted at MIS Al-Hilaal Wanakarta, located in Wanakarta Village, Lolong Guba District, Buru Regency. This location was chosen for its relevance to the study on the effect of teacher discipline on the quality of teaching and learning. The research is planned to take place over one to three months, during which data will be collected and processed.

The research instruments include observations of teacher discipline. These observations aim to gather concrete and in-depth information on the quality of teaching and learning at MIS Al-Hilaal Wanakarta. The primary focus is the discipline behavior of teachers during the learning process. Through this, the researcher seeks to understand the effectiveness of education delivery and the teaching standards implemented at the school.

Another instrument used is a questionnaire, distributed to respondents in written form using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly Agree" (5) to "Strongly Disagree" (1). The use of this structured questionnaire aims to collect systematic and statistically analyzable data. It is designed to objectively and measurably assess respondents' perceptions of the variables being studied.

Documentation was used to collect written information from the school relevant to the study, such as teacher and student records. Data collection techniques included the distribution and retrieval

of questionnaires while adhering to ethical research standards, such as participant consent and data confidentiality. Once collected, the data were verified and coded in preparation for further analysis.

The population in this study consists of all 12 teachers at MIS Al-Hilaal Wanakarta. Due to the small size and accessibility of the population, saturated sampling was used. Data sources include primary data collected through questionnaires and secondary data from school documents. Data tabulation involves organizing the data into statistical tables such as frequency and mean values to ease interpretation.

Data analysis begins with descriptive statistics to understand the data characteristics. Instrument validity is tested using the product moment correlation, and reliability is measured with Cronbach's Alpha ($\alpha \geq 0.6$). Further analysis includes simple linear regression, determination coefficient (R^2), t-test (partial), F-test (simultaneous), and hypothesis testing using the Spearman Rank correlation (ρ) to measure the relationship between two ordinal variables. Each analytical step aims to provide a deeper understanding of the interrelationships among the studied variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity Test

The validity test was conducted to determine whether the questionnaire used in this study is valid. A questionnaire is considered valid if the calculated correlation coefficient (r-count) exceeds the critical value from the r-table obtained after calculating the degree of freedom (df) and comparing it with the SPSS results. The formula used is $df = n - 2$, where df is the degree of freedom and n is the number of respondents. In this study, there were 12 respondents, resulting in a df of 10. According to the r-table, a degree of freedom of 10 corresponds to a critical value of 0.4973. Below is the result of the validity test for the questionnaire items related to the teacher discipline variable.

Table 1. presents the validity test results for the teacher discipline dimension. The indicators measured include teacher compliance with school regulations, teacher punctuality in the school environment, teachers' awareness in carrying out their duties, and their responsibility in completing tasks. Each indicator is represented by three questions, and all questions have a correlation coefficient (r-count) greater than the r-table value (0.4973), indicating their validity at a 0.05 significance level. The highest r-count value observed was 1.000, and the lowest still exceeded the critical threshold, affirming the validity of all items.

Table 1. Validity Test Discipline

No	Questionnaire Item Description	Question	r-count	r-table	Sig. Level	Remark
1	Teacher Compliance with School Rules	Q1	1.000	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q2	1.000	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q3	0.909	0.4973	0.05	Valid
2	Teacher Punctuality in the School Environment	Q1	0.670	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q2	0.845	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q3	1.000	0.4973	0.05	Valid
3	Teacher Awareness in Performing Duties	Q1	0.909	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q2	0.770	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q3	0.781	0.4973	0.05	Valid
4	Teacher Responsibility in Carrying Out Duties	Q1	0.798	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q2	0.798	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q3	0.828	0.4973	0.05	Valid

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results, Version 30

Based on the validity test results in Table 1., all question items across the four tested indicators have a correlation coefficient (r-count) greater than the r-table value of 0.4973 at a 0.05 significance level. Referring to the criteria proposed by Arikunto, it can be concluded that all the question items in this research instrument are valid and suitable to be used as a measurement tool in the study.

Table 2. Validity Test Quality Education

No	Questionnaire Item Description	Question	r-count	r-table	Sig. Level	Remark
1	Teacher Behavior	Q1	1.000	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q2	0.756	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q3	0.707	0.4973	0.05	Valid
2	Student Behavior and Learning Impact	Q1	0.735	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q2	0.756	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q3	0.756	0.4973	0.05	Valid
3	Learning Climate	Q1	0.891	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q2	0.891	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q3	0.707	0.4973	0.05	Valid
4	Learning Materials	Q1	0.707	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q2	0.707	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q3	0.756	0.4973	0.05	Valid
5	Learning Media	Q1	0.707	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q2	0.707	0.4973	0.05	Valid
		Q3	0.707	0.4973	0.05	Valid

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results, Version 30

Table 2 shows the validity test results for the learning quality dimension. The measured indicators include teacher behavior, student behavior and learning outcomes, learning climate, learning materials, and learning media. Each indicator contains three question items, and all of them show correlation coefficients (r-count) higher than the critical r-table value (0.4973) at a 0.05 significance level. These findings further confirm that the instruments used for assessing learning quality are statistically valid.

The results of the validity test analysis for the research instruments indicate that all the question items used in the questionnaire meet the established validity criteria. This validity is demonstrated by comparing the correlation coefficient (r-count) with the critical value (r-table) at a 0.05 significance level, where all question items yield an r-count greater than the r-table value of 0.4973.

Reliability Test

The reliability analysis used is Cronbach's Alpha. A measurement tool is considered reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient obtained is equal to or greater than 0.60 (Arikunto, 2010). The following are the results of the reliability test using SPSS for the instrument used in the study. The reliability results for Variable X (Teacher Discipline).

Table 3. Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items
Teacher Discipline (Variable X)	0.783	0.982	13
Teaching Process Quality	0.777	0.983	16

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results, Version 30

The results from the reliability test indicate that the Cronbach's Alpha value for the Teacher Discipline variable is 0.783, which exceeds the threshold of 0.60 (Arikunto, 2010), with 13 items in the

questionnaire. Similarly, for the Teaching Process Quality variable, the Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.777, also above the 0.60 threshold, with 16 items. These results confirm that the questionnaires used for both variables are reliable.

Simple Linear Regression Test

1. Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2)

The coefficient of determination is used to predict the extent of the contribution of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y). Below are the results from the SPSS version 30 test:

Table 4. Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.719	0.517	0.468	5.65279

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results, Version 30

Based on the results of the coefficient of determination test shown in Table 4.24, the R Square (R^2) value is 0.517, or 51.7%. This indicates that the independent variable, which is the teacher discipline dimension, can explain or influence the dependent variable (the quality of the teaching-learning process) by 51.7%. The correlation value (R) of 0.719 shows a strong relationship between the teacher discipline dimension and the quality of the teaching-learning process.

Meanwhile, the Adjusted R Square value of 0.468, or 46.8%, provides a more realistic view of the model's ability to explain the variation in the dependent variable, as it has accounted for the number of independent variables in the model. The standard error of estimation of 5.65279 indicates the level of prediction error in the regression model. From these results, it can be concluded that there are still about 48.3% of other factors, outside of the teacher discipline dimension, that influence the quality of the teaching-learning process and are not included in this model.

2. Partial Test (t)

The t-test is conducted to show how much influence the independent variable has on the related variable. If the significance value is less than 0.05, it means the variable significantly affects the other variable.

Table 6. Partial Test (t)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
1	(Constant)	25.849	11.458	2.256
	Teacher Discipline Dimension	0.751	0.230	0.719

Source: SPSS Data Analysis Results, Version 30

Based on the calculations shown in Table 6, the t value for the teacher discipline dimension is 3.269, which is greater than the t-table value of 1.812, with a significance value of 0.008. Since the significance value (0.008) is less than the 0.05 significance level (5%), it indicates that the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted. Therefore, the teacher discipline dimension has a significant effect on the quality of the teaching-learning process. This is further supported by the positive regression coefficient (B) of 0.751, indicating a positive influence of the teacher discipline dimension on the quality of the teaching-learning process. In other words, for every one-unit increase in teacher discipline, the quality of the teaching-learning process increases by 0.751 units.

Thus, the research hypothesis stating that the teacher discipline dimension affects the quality of the teaching-learning process is accepted. This finding suggests that teacher discipline plays a crucial role in determining the quality of the learning process in the classroom.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the results of the regression analysis demonstrate a significant relationship between teacher discipline and the quality of the teaching-learning process. The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.517 indicates that teacher discipline explains 51.7% of the variation in the

quality of the teaching-learning process, signifying a moderate but substantial impact. The strong correlation ($R = 0.719$) further supports the existence of this relationship. The t-test results show that the teacher discipline dimension has a statistically significant effect on teaching quality, with a positive regression coefficient of 0.751. This suggests that improvements in teacher discipline positively influence the quality of the teaching-learning process. Moreover, the F-test results indicate that teacher discipline, as the independent variable, significantly impacts the dependent variable, the teaching-learning process. With a significant F-value (10.683) and a p-value of 0.008, it can be concluded that the regression model is valid, and teacher discipline plays a crucial role in enhancing the quality of education.

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